

LIVING WITH SCHIZOPHRENIA DURING THE EARLY COVID-19 PANDEMIC: A QUALITATIVE STUDY OF COMMUNITY MENTAL HEALTH CENTER SERVICE USERS IN TURKEY**COVID-19 PANDEMİSİNİN ERKEN DÖNEMİNDE ŞİZOFRENİ İLE YAŞAMAK: TÜRKİYE'DE TOPLUM RUH SAĞLIĞI MERKEZİ HİZMET KULLANICILARIYLA NİTEL BİR ÇALIŞMA**Yadigar ÇEVİK DURMAZ¹, Berna ERSOY ÖZCAN²¹Munzur University, Psychiatric Nursing, Tunceli, Türkiye²Sinop University, Psychiatric Nursing, Sinop, Türkiye**ABSTRACT****Objective:** This qualitative study explored how people living with schizophrenia and receiving care from a Community Mental Health Center (CMHC) in Turkey experienced the first year of the COVID-19 pandemic, focusing on the meanings attributed to COVID-19, protective practices, everyday life, treatment continuity, and family relationships.**Methods:** Using purposive sampling, semi-structured telephone interviews were conducted with 20 CMHC service users diagnosed with schizophrenia between 20 December 2020 and 1 February 2021. Participants were in remission, had sufficient cognitive capacity to participate, and volunteered for the study. Interviews lasted approximately 30–40 minutes, were audio-recorded with permission, transcribed verbatim, and analyzed using Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis. Descriptive data were summarized using frequencies and percentages, and reporting followed the COREQ checklist.**Results:** Three overarching themes emerged: (1) meanings attributed to COVID-19, (2) measures taken to protect against COVID-19, and (3) the effects of the pandemic on life, treatment, and family relationships. Participants reported adopting protective behaviors, experiencing restricted mobility and social interactions, and facing emotional and financial difficulties. Barriers to accessing hospital and CMHC services, as well as challenges in medication and prescription-report renewal, were commonly reported. Some participants purchased medications out of pocket to maintain treatment continuity.**Conclusion:** The first year of the COVID-19 pandemic created significant psychosocial and healthcare access challenges for individuals living with schizophrenia. Findings highlight the need for crisis-ready community mental health services that ensure uninterrupted medication access, facilitate prescription renewals, provide proactive follow-up and remote consultation options, and strengthen family and caregiver support during future public health emergencies.**Keywords:** Community Mental Health Services, COVID-19, Qualitative Research, Schizophrenia, Service Continuity**ÖZET****Amaç:** Bu nitel çalışma, Türkiye'deki bir Toplum Ruh Sağlığı Merkezi'nde (TSM) şizofreni tanısı almış kişilerin COVID-19 pandemisinin ilk yılını nasıl deneyimlediklerini, COVID-19'a atfedilen anlamlar, koruyucu uygulamalar, günlük yaşam, tedavi sürekliliği ve aile ilişkileri konularına odaklanarak araştırmıştır.**Yöntemler:** Amaçlı örnekleme yöntemi kullanılarak, 20 Aralık 2020 ile 1 Şubat 2021 tarihleri arasında şizofreni tanısı almış 20 TSM hizmet kullanıcısıyla yarı yapılandırılmış telefon görüşmeleri yapılmıştır. Katılımcılar remisyonda olup, çalışmaya katılmak için yeterli bilişsel kapasiteye sahip ve gönüllü olarak katılmışlardır. Görüşmeler yaklaşık 30-40 dakika sürmüş, izin alınarak ses kaydı alınmış, kelimesi kelimesine yazıya dökülmüş ve Braun ve Clarke'ın tematik analizi kullanılarak analiz edilmiştir. Tanımlayıcı veriler frekanslar ve yüzdeler kullanılarak özetlenmiş ve raporlama COREQ kontrol listesine göre yapılmıştır.**Bulgular:** Üç ana tema ortaya çıktı: (1) COVID-19'a atfedilen anlamlar, (2) COVID-19'a karşı korunmak için alınan önlemler ve (3) pandeminin yaşam, tedavi ve aile ilişkileri üzerindeki etkileri. Katılımcılar koruyucu davranışlar benimsediklerini, hareket ve sosyal etkileşimlerinde kısıtlamalar yaşadıklarını ve duygusal ve mali zorluklarla karşılaştıklarını bildirdiler. Hastane ve toplum ruh sağlığı hizmetlerine erişimdeki engellerin yanı sıra ilaç ve reçete yenileme zorlukları yaygın olarak bildirildi. Bazı katılımcılar, tedavi sürekliliğini sağlamak için ilaçları kendi ceplerinden satın aldılar.**Sonuç:** COVID-19 pandemisinin ilk yılı, şizofreni ile yaşayan bireyler için önemli psikososyal ve sağlık hizmetlerine erişim zorlukları yarattı. Bulgular, kesintisiz ilaç erişimini sağlayan, reçete yenilemelerini kolaylaştıran, proaktif takip ve uzaktan danışma seçenekleri sunan ve gelecekteki halk sağlığı acil durumlarında aile ve bakıcı desteğini güçlendiren krize hazır toplum ruh sağlığı hizmetlerine duyulan ihtiyacı vurgulamaktadır.**Anahtar Kelimeler:** COVID-19, Hizmet Sürekliliği, Nitel Araştırma, Şizofreni, Toplum Ruh Sağlığı Hizmetleri**Corresponding author:** Yadigar ÇEVİK DURMAZ, Psychiatric Nursing, Munzur University, Tunceli, Turkey .**E-mail:** ycevik@munzur.edu.tr**Cite this article:** DURMAZ, Ç.Y., ÖZCAN, E.B. (2026). Living With Schizophrenia During The Early Covid-19 Pandemic: A Qualitative Study Of Community Mental Health Center Service Users In Turkey. *Gevher Nesibe Journal of Medical & Health Science*. 11(2), 198- 205. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20845370>

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted daily life, social participation, and access to health services on a global scale. Quarantine, lockdowns, social distancing rules, and uncertainty about the course of the outbreak negatively affected psychological well-being and altered everyday routines, including mobility, social relationships, physical activity, and sleep patterns (Di Renzo et al., 2020; Moreno et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020; World Health Organization, 2020). Evidence from the general population showed increases in stress, anxiety, depression, and loneliness during the pandemic period (Vindegaard and Benros, 2020; Xiong et al., 2020).

These disruptions were especially important for people living with severe mental illness. Individuals with schizophrenia may be more vulnerable during outbreaks because social isolation, misinformation, fear of infection, and interruptions in routine care can worsen distress and reduce access to support (Brown et al., 2020; Ozdin and Bayrak Ozdin, 2020; Page et al., 2011). Restrictions may also change family relationships because patients spend more time at home and depend more heavily on relatives for everyday functioning and care.

Community Mental Health Centers (CMHCs) play a central role in follow-up, psychosocial support, and continuity of treatment for people living with schizophrenia. During the pandemic, however, changes in service delivery, delayed appointments, and difficulties in prescription renewal may have created important gaps in care (Moreno et al., 2020; Tozoglu et al., 2021; Usta Saglam et al., 2022).

Documenting experiences during the first year of the pandemic is valuable because it captures the challenges faced by a group with substantial support needs during a period of major service disruption and can inform preparedness for future public health emergencies. Therefore, this study aimed to explore how people living with schizophrenia and receiving care from a CMHC in Turkey experienced the first pandemic year, with particular focus on meanings attributed to COVID-19, protective practices, daily life, treatment continuity, and family relationships.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This study used a qualitative descriptive design to provide a straightforward account of participants' experiences and service-access needs. A purposive sampling strategy was used to recruit CMHC service users with direct experience relevant to the research question. Data were collected between 20 December 2020 and 1 February 2021.

The study population consisted of individuals with schizophrenia registered at a CMHC in Turkey. Participants were eligible if they volunteered to participate, were in remission, and had sufficient cognitive capacity to complete a telephone interview. Data collection continued until thematic saturation was reached. Twenty participants were included (13 men and 7 women).

Because of pandemic restrictions and infection risk, data were collected through semi-structured telephone interviews. Before the interviews, written informed consent was obtained by e-mail from participants and, where applicable, their legal guardians; verbal consent was reconfirmed at the start of each interview. A Personal Information Form and a Semi-Structured Interview Form developed from the literature were used to guide data collection. The interview guide explored participants' views on the meaning of COVID-19, protective behaviors, treatment access, everyday life, and family relationships. Interviews lasted approximately 30-40 minutes, including completion of the descriptive questions.

The interviewer had previously worked as a nurse at the same CMHC and therefore knew some participants in a clinical context. This previous experience facilitated rapport and helped participants speak in detail about their experiences. To reduce the effect of prior familiarity on interpretation, the researcher kept reflexive notes during data collection and analysis, and emerging codes and themes were discussed within the research team.

Interviews were audio-recorded with permission, transcribed verbatim, and analyzed using Braun and Clarke's six-phase thematic analysis approach (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Each transcript was read repeatedly to achieve immersion in the data. Initial codes were generated independently by the researchers, compared, and refined through discussion until consensus was reached. Related codes were grouped into categories and then into overarching themes and sub-themes. Descriptive characteristics from the Personal Information Form were summarized in SPSS using frequencies and percentages. Reporting of the study was guided by the COREQ checklist (Tong et al., 2007).

Credibility was strengthened through familiarity with the field, audio-recording, verbatim transcription, independent coding by more than one researcher, and team discussions about coding decisions. The use of verbatim quotations supported confirmability, while clear descriptions of the study context, participants, and analytic process were used to enhance transferability and dependability.

Ethics approval for this study was obtained from the Munzur University Non-Interventional Research Ethics Committee (Meeting No: 5, Decision No: 7, Date: 29 May 2020). The committee reviewed the study entitled "The Effect of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the Lifestyle of Patients with Schizophrenia" and determined that it was ethically appropriate. Institutional permission was obtained from the relevant Community Mental Health Center prior to data collection. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants and, where applicable, from their legal guardians. Verbal consent was reconfirmed at the beginning of each telephone interview. Participants were informed that participation was voluntary, that they could withdraw from the study at any time without consequence, and that all information would be kept confidential and used solely for scientific purposes. The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

RESULTS

Participants were 22 to 63 years old. Most were male (65.0%), single (70.0%), and living in the city center (55.0%). Most participants had been living with schizophrenia and using medication for 10 years or longer, and 95.0% reported regular medication use during the pandemic (Table 1).

Table 1. Participant characteristics (n=20)

Variable	Category	n (%)
Gender	Male	13 (65.0)
	Female	7 (35.0)
Age (years)	22	1 (5.0)
	31	2 (10.0)
	32	1 (5.0)
	33	1 (5.0)
	34	1 (5.0)
	35	2 (10.0)
	39	1 (5.0)
	40	2 (10.0)
	43	1 (5.0)
	44	1 (5.0)
	45	1 (5.0)
	47	1 (5.0)
	48	1 (5.0)
	51	2 (10.0)
	55	1 (5.0)
63	1 (5.0)	
Education	Primary school	7 (35.0)
	Secondary school	6 (30.0)

Variable	Category	n (%)	
	High school	4 (20.0)	
	University	3 (15.0)	
Marital status	Married	6 (30.0)	
	Single	14 (70.0)	
Place of residence	Village	6 (30.0)	
	District	2 (10.0)	
	City center	11 (55.0)	
	Not reported	1 (5.0)	
Economic status	Income less than expenses	13 (65.0)	
	Income more than expenses	7 (35.0)	
Living arrangement	Family (unspecified)	11 (55.0)	
	Mother	4 (20.0)	
Living arrangement	Spouse	3 (15.0)	
	Sibling	2 (10.0)	
Duration of illness/medication use	6 years	1 (5.0)	
	7 years	1 (5.0)	
	10 years	6 (30.0)	
	12 years	1 (5.0)	
	14 years	2 (10.0)	
	15 years	3 (15.0)	
	16 years	1 (5.0)	
	29 years	1 (5.0)	
	35 years	1 (5.0)	
	37 years	2 (10.0)	
	Not reported	1 (5.0)	
Number of hospitalizations	0	4 (20.0)	
	1	7 (35.0)	
	2	1 (5.0)	
	3	1 (5.0)	
	4	2 (10.0)	
	5	2 (10.0)	
	10	1 (5.0)	
	Not reported	2 (10.0)	
	Going out before the COVID-19 pandemic	Yes	18 (90.0)
		No	2 (10.0)
Frequency of going out before the COVID-19 pandemic	Rarely	7 (35.0)	
	Often	4 (20.0)	
	Every day	6 (30.0)	
	Not reported	3 (15.0)	
Regular medication use during the COVID-19 pandemic	Yes	19 (95.0)	
	No	1 (5.0)	

Note: Percentages are based on n=20. 'Not reported' denotes data unavailable in the original dataset.

Three main themes were identified: (1) meanings attributed to COVID-19, (2) measures taken to protect against COVID-19, and (3) effects of the pandemic on life, treatment, and family relationships (Table 2).

Table 2. Main themes and categories identified in the thematic analysis

Main theme	Categories
Meanings attributed to COVID-19	Disease or flu-like illness; virus/microbe; fatality; uncertain origin or laboratory-production claims
Measures taken to protect against COVID-19	Masks/protective equipment; social isolation and physical distancing; hygiene; vaccination
Effects on life, treatment, and family relationships	Restricted mobility and social contact; emotional and financial strain; hospital/CMHC access and medication-report renewal; family tension, fear, grief, or no major change

Note: Categories may overlap within individual participant narratives.

Meanings Attributed to Covid-19

Participants most often described COVID-19 as a disease or as a virus/microbe. Some viewed it as a temporary flu-like illness, whereas others emphasized that it was fatal. A smaller group associated COVID-19 with its origin in China and repeated uncertain information about laboratory production. Together, these responses suggested that participants followed public discussions about the pandemic but interpreted them through varying levels of certainty and fear.

Representative statements included: "A disease like pneumonia, like the flu" (P2), "A dangerous, fatal virus" (P20), and "It was produced on purpose in the laboratory... but I am not sure" (P12).

Measures Taken to Protect Against Covid-19

Protective measures centered on masks, social isolation, physical distancing, and hygiene. Participants commonly said they avoided leaving home unless necessary and used masks when they had to go out. Some also reported changing clothes or washing hands immediately after returning home. Only one participant explicitly reported vaccination. Illustrative statements included: "I do not go out. If I have to, I wear a mask" (P9), "I wear two masks" (P14), and "I change the clothes I wear outside when I arrive home and wash them immediately" (P20).

Effects of Covid-19 On Life, Treatment and Family Relationships

The pandemic affected participants' lives most clearly through the restriction of going outdoors and seeing other people. Participants described boredom, distress, loneliness, and anger when they could not walk, visit relatives, or receive visitors. For some, these experiences were compounded by financial difficulty because family members could not work. A few participants, especially those who reported rarely going out before the pandemic or living in villages, felt that their daily lives had changed little.

Participants said: "It affected my act of going out. I cannot walk. I cannot go to the park and visit my mother" (P1), "We cannot go out. I am constantly distressed" (P2), and "My family cannot work... we are having financial difficulty" (P13).

Continuity of treatment was disrupted for several participants. Delayed hospital appointments, difficulty attending the CMHC, and problems renewing medication reports were frequently mentioned barriers. These disruptions sometimes resulted in out-of-pocket medication purchases. Other participants stated that their treatment continued without major problems.

Participants stated: "I cannot go to the hospital. My appointments are delayed" (P4), "I cannot go to the community mental health center" (P19), "I could not renew my report. I have to buy my drugs with money" (P17), and "It did not affect. I can go to the hospital" (P14).

Family relationships were mixed. Some participants reported increased tension and communication problems because family members were confined together for long periods. Others described fear and sadness related to infection or bereavement within the family, while a small number reported no major change in family relationships. A few narratives also referred to excessive cleaning behaviors or relocation during the pandemic period.

Illustrative statements included: "We are all angry because we are at home. This creates tension" (P5), "My family members are scared, my mother died" (P8), and "My family relationships were not affected" (P1).

DISCUSSION

A central finding of this study is that the first pandemic year was experienced primarily through restriction: not being able to go out, see other people, or access routine services as before. These experiences were accompanied by boredom, distress, loneliness, and anger. This

is consistent with earlier work showing that quarantine and social isolation negatively affect mental health and can intensify loneliness and uncertainty (Brooks et al., 2020; Leigh-Hunt et al., 2017; Vindegaard and Benros, 2020).

Participants generally demonstrated awareness of COVID-19 as an infectious disease and reported using masks, distancing, and hygiene measures. This finding suggests that people living with schizophrenia were able to understand and apply public health guidance despite the stressful context. Some narratives also echoed circulating uncertainty and misinformation, including claims about laboratory production. Because the interviews did not include a clinical assessment of symptom content, these statements cannot be interpreted as evidence of paranoid ideation; they are better situated within the broader misinformation environment. Nevertheless, clinicians should explore whether alarming or conspiratorial information increases fear or suspiciousness and provide clear, repeated, accessible information through trusted care channels (Hemmer et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2020; Williams et al., 2020).

Another important finding was the fragility of treatment continuity. Difficulties attending hospital or CMHC appointments and renewing medication reports meant that some participants faced direct threats to treatment adherence. Similar service disruptions have been reported in other pandemic-era studies involving psychosis and community mental health care (Kirli et al., 2020; Moreno et al., 2020; Tozoglu et al., 2021; Usta Saglam et al., 2022). For community mental health practice, these findings point to proactive telephone follow-up, flexible prescription and medication-report renewal procedures, remote consultation options, and practical support for medication access during emergencies. In Turkey, contingency planning could include time-limited electronic extension of medication reports, pharmacy dispensing pathways during appointment disruptions, and CMHC outreach lists for service users at greatest risk of interrupted care.

Family life functioned as both a source of support and a source of strain. Some participants said their relationships were unchanged, but many described tension, fear, grief, and conflict related to prolonged co-residence, caregiving burden, or illness and death in the family. These mixed findings are important because family context can either buffer or intensify distress in schizophrenia, particularly when community services are disrupted (Bhattacharjee and Acharya, 2020; Verdolini et al., 2021). In addition to patient-focused services, emergency plans should offer family caregivers brief psychoeducation, telephone counseling, and referral pathways for grief, burden, and conflict.

Because the interviews were conducted between December 2020 and February 2021, the study reflects the first pandemic year, specifically the winter of 2020-2021, rather than the earliest outbreak weeks or later phases of the pandemic. This timing is a strength because it documents experiences while major disruptions were ongoing, but the findings should be interpreted as historically situated. Crisis preparedness planning for future outbreaks should explicitly include people living with severe mental illness, especially in relation to medication continuity, outreach to those who cannot travel, and family-focused psychosocial support.

The study has several limitations. It was conducted in a single CMHC with a relatively small sample, so transferability is limited. Telephone interviews may have constrained depth compared with face-to-face interviews, and the findings reflect self-reported experiences during a specific period. The interviews did not include a standardized assessment of psychotic symptoms; therefore, comments about misinformation cannot be interpreted as evidence of paranoid ideation or linked to symptom severity. Nevertheless, the study provides detailed qualitative evidence from a group whose perspectives are often underrepresented in emergency planning.

CONCLUSION

This study shows that, for people living with schizophrenia, the first year of the COVID-19 pandemic was characterized by restricted mobility, reduced social contact, emotional distress, family strain, and interruptions in access to community-based care. Crisis-ready community mental health systems should ensure uninterrupted medication access and medication-report renewal, proactive telephone or remote follow-up, transport or outreach alternatives for those unable to attend services, and structured support for family caregivers. These measures may reduce avoidable treatment interruptions and psychosocial strain during future public health emergencies.

Acknowledgement

This study did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors. The authors have no acknowledgments to declare.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest regarding the research.

Author Contributions

All authors contributed equally.

Funding

The research does not have any financial support.

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